

On a possible component of the magnetic field of neutron stars

Valery Borisovich Morozov¹

¹Gamalei 11-2-24, 123098, Moscow, Russia.

To cite this article:

Valery Borisovich Morozov. “On a possible component of the magnetic field of neutron stars”, *Parana Journal of Science and Education*. Vol. 6, No. 4, 2020, pp. 76-78. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3880605>

Received: June 02, 2020; **Accepted:** June 4, 2020; **Published:** June 5, 2020.

Abstract

The author’s purpose in this article is to draw readers’ attention to the magnetic properties of the neutron component of the neutron stars. Under high pressure, the neutrons form the Bose-Einstein condensate of triplet Cooper pairs of neutrons. This superfluid condensate is a ferromagnetic having a domain structure. That is why it is reasonably to consider a neutron star as a magnetic multipole. This suggests existence of a dipole magnetic moment of a neutron star as a result of spontaneous magnetization of neutron superfluid liquid. The connection is noted of the magnetic dipole moment of a neutron star with its mechanical moment.

Keywords: Neutron stars, Bose condensate, Ferromagnetism.

¹ Email: valery_morozov@hotmail.com

1. Introduction

The neutron stars attract ever increasing interest as objects with extreme states of matter and extreme gravitational and magnetic fields [1, 2].

A gravitational field of a neutron star is well described by the general relativity theory. The Einstein equation with a given energy-momentum-tension tensor of neutron star substance² enables determining the metric tensor describing the gravitational field.

It is widely accepted that the magnetic field of the neutron stars is created by quasi-stationary currents of charged quasi-particles in the substance of the neutron stars. Here we consider another source of the magnetic field of the neutron stars.

2. Bose-Einstein condensate of Cooper pairs of ³He isotope and neutron pairs

There are strong arguments in favor of the assumption that the main component of the neutron stars substance is the neutron [2]. Some idea of the nucleons interaction in a high-density Fermi liquid is given by the studies of the neutrons interaction in the atomic nucleus [3]. In this paper and in similar works, the existence of the Cooper neutron pairs is substantiated. Upon that, it is stated that possible is existence of both singlet and triplet interlinking of neutrons with a non-zero orbital moment.

As a rule in the papers, the direct analogy is used between the properties of the condensed state of the neutron liquid and the properties of the liquid phases of the helium isotope ³He. Indeed, both a neutron and ³He fermions have a negative magnetic moment and a strong repulsive potential.

The phases of the liquid ³He have been studied quite well and experimentally particularly [4, 5]. We can make up for the lack of information about the neutron condensate and fill the gap if to use the analogy between the ³He isotope liquid state and the neutron liquid.

Figure 1. Phases of helium isotope ³He.

Source: Author.

With a decrease in temperature at $T = T_c$ the liquid ³He isotope passes through the second-order phase transition and is changed to the superfluid state. The ³He isotope is known to have three phases in the liquid state (see the $p - T - H$ phase diagram in Figure (1)): the normal Fermi liquid N ; the superfluid consisting of the singlet Cooper pairs of the quasi-particles B ; and the superfluid consisting of the triplet Cooper pairs of the isotope ³He A . In a magnetic field, the phase A is changed to the phase A_1 distinguished with regular magnetic arrangement.

In all their superfluid phases, the Cooper pairs have the non-zero orbital moment of momentum of the quasi-particles in the pair $L=1$. The Cooper pairs of various superfluid phases of the isotope ³He differ in their projections of spin and angular momentum on the quantization axes direction. Due to the macroscopic coherence, all the Cooper pairs in the Bose condensate have a common direction of the quantization axes of the spin and the angular momentum. Therefore, the superfluid phases of the ³He isotope have the orbital and magnetic anisotropy. Thus, they are liquid crystals and well-oriented magnetic substances at the same time.

The ferromagnetic nature of the phase A of the superfluid ³He isotope is confirmed by the domain structure of the ³He-based films [5].

3. Magnetic field of neutron stars

Usually, a spontaneous magnetization of ferromagnets occurs due to an exchange interaction of magnetic moments (Stoner model of

² Strictly speaking, with regard to a neutron star, this tensor should include its magnetic field, too.

collective electrons in metals) [7]. The neutron pairs are bosons. In a neutron star, its mass density is an order of magnitude higher than that in a nucleus. This should lead to the condensate formation with the same spin, orbital and magnetic moments.

In general, a neutron star containing such a condensate should be a magnetic multipole consisting of domains.

The magnetic dipole moment of a neutron star is related to the angular momentum. This follows from the correlation between the magnetic moment and the orbital moment in the Cooper pair of neutrons. From a macroscopic point of view, this connection of the moments of a neutron star as a whole represents both the Barnett effect and the (opposite to it) Einstein – de Haase effect [8].

4. Conclusion

It does not follow from the foregoing that the current mechanism of formation of the magnetic field of neutron stars, which is now accepted, is impossible. On the contrary, both mechanisms can coexist and form both a dipole moment and a more complex multipole magnetic field.

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